

Ключові слова: бізнес-комунікація, цінності, етика, довіра, прозорість.

Khilkovska Asia. Business Communication 2.0: Rethinking the Philosophy.

The author addresses the need to update and modernize the content of the discipline *Business English*, an essential component of many Higher education programmes. The paper examines the advantages of *Market Leader*, a course widely used in Ukrainian universities, whose structure and materials kept it relevant for many years. The author argues for supplementing the course with a broad range of up to date English language sources—from leading economic publications (*The Economist, Financial Times, Harvard Business Review*) to contemporary educational platforms for entrepreneurs and start ups (startup.info, Pleadly Blog, etc.). Being used in class, these resources ensure continuous alignment with the dynamics of the modern business environment, where new entrepreneurial models, development trends, and communication practices are formed.

The analysis of recent methodological publications highlights the areas of the discipline that require content renewal in order to equip learners with communication skills relevant to today's rapidly evolving business context. Scholarly literature emphasizes the importance of focusing on practical professional competencies, including models such as the **4Cs** (communication, collaboration, critical thinking, creativity). Researchers also underscore the role of Business English as a **Lingua Franca**, which necessitates the development of linguacultural competencies. Additional priorities include building skills in digital communication tools, mastering new models of corporate interaction, and acquiring contemporary business terminology that reflects global market trends.

However, the author argues that it is equally important to draw learners' attention to significant shifts in modern business philosophy, which directly influence language use and communication models. These shifts include the movement from a "profit above all" paradigm toward values such as ethics, trust, transparency, social responsibility, sustainability, and inclusivity; the transition "from hierarchy to a team," which transforms interaction within organizations and among stakeholders; and the shift "from technocratic to philosophical and reflective thinking."

Engagement with current sources provides learners not only with access to the latest business practices but also with understanding of contemporary business philosophy, which is crucial, as effective business communication relies on the ability to articulate one's own values clearly and to understand the values of others—skills that underpin the success of both entrepreneurs and employees.

Key words: business communication, values, ethics, trust, transparency.

М. Ф. Чемоданова

**POST-EDITING MACHINE TRANSLATION AS AN EDUCATIONAL TREND:
EVIDENCE-BASED PREDICTIONS FOR PHILOLOGICAL EDUCATION
IN UKRAINE**

In the context of rapid technological advancement, **machine translation (MT)** has become an integral component of contemporary linguistic practice, exerting a significant influence on both the translation industry and language education. While MT tools are increasingly used in academic and professional settings, research in translation pedagogy indicates that **uncritical or untrained reliance on MT may negatively affect the development of students' linguistic, analytical, and translational competencies**. This situation reveals a clear gap in pedagogical models that seek to balance technological innovation with the formation of professional language skills.

Against this background, **post-editing of machine translation (PEMT)**—defined as the systematic correction and refinement of machine-generated output to meet predefined quality standards—has emerged as both a востребованная professional competence and an essential component of modern translator training. Empirical studies demonstrate that structured training in post-editing practices contributes to improved

translation quality, heightened metalinguistic awareness, and more effective learning outcomes among students [4, c. 28].

Within higher education, translation and philological curricula increasingly incorporate **dedicated PEMT modules**, reflecting broader shifts in competency-based educational frameworks that prioritize digital literacy alongside traditional linguistic and cultural knowledge. In Ukraine, several academic institutions have already integrated post-editing courses into translator training programs, aiming to prepare graduates for the current and projected demands of the translation market shaped by artificial intelligence and automation.

International scholarship further confirms the didactic potential of PEMT, showing that post-editing tasks foster **critical thinking, error analysis, and decision-making skills**, which are fundamental to professional translation practice. Through evaluating MT output, identifying linguistic and pragmatic inconsistencies, and producing context-appropriate revisions, students actively engage in cognitively complex processes that enhance both linguistic competence and professional judgment.

Machine translation post-editing combines **automated efficiency with human linguistic expertise**, enabling translators to meet quality expectations in a time-effective manner. Distinctions between light and full post-editing workflows illustrate varying quality requirements and levels of linguistic intervention, each corresponding to specific professional and educational objectives. As an educational tool, PEMT thus performs a dual function: it mirrors real-world translation practices while simultaneously supporting the development of critical language awareness and technological competence [2, c. 32].

The integration of PEMT into philological education offers several clear advantages. First, it ensures closer **alignment with labor market expectations**, as employers increasingly require translators to work confidently with MT systems. Second, post-editing activities enhance **linguistic sensitivity and stylistic accuracy**, bridging the gap between machine-generated output and human communicative standards. Third, PEMT strengthens students' **digital competence**, increasing their readiness to operate within contemporary translation environments.

Despite these benefits, the systematic incorporation of PEMT into Ukrainian philological curricula presents certain challenges. These include the need for **specialized instructor training**, the development of **reliable assessment frameworks** for evaluating post-editing competence, and the alignment of curricular innovations with **national educational standards and international benchmarks** [3, c. 42].

Addressing these issues requires evidence-based forecasting to ensure that educational reforms remain both pedagogically sound and professionally relevant.

This paper therefore examines current empirical and theoretical evidence on the role of PEMT in translator education and offers **data-driven predictions** regarding its future impact on philological training in Ukraine. It argues that the strategic and systematic integration of post-editing practices will play a crucial role in modernizing philological education and enhancing the professional preparedness of future translators.

References

1. Bowker, L., Ciro, J. B. (2019). *Machine Translation and Global Research: Towards Improved Machine Translation Literacy in the Scholarly Community*. Bingley: Emerald Publishing, 220 p.
2. Doherty, S., Kenny, D. (2014). The design and evaluation of a statistical machine translation syllabus for translation students. *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 8 (2), pp. 295–315.
3. O'Brien, S. (2011). Towards a dynamic quality evaluation model for translation. *Journal of Specialised Translation*, 17, pp. 55–77.
4. Vieira, L. N., O'Brien, S. and O'Hagan, M. (2020). Understanding the role of post-editing in translator training. *Translation and Interpreting Studies*, 15 (1), pp. 1–26.
5. Kenny, D., Doherty, S. (2014). Statistical machine translation in the translation curriculum: overcoming obstacles and empowering translators. *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 8 (2), pp. 276–294.
6. UNESCO (2023). *Guidance on Generative AI in Education and Research* [online]. Paris: UNESCO. Available at: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/guidance-generative-ai-education-and-research> [Accessed 20 Dec. 2025].
7. European Commission (2022). *Language Technologies and Translation in the Digital Age* [online]. Brussels. Available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu> [Accessed 18 Dec. 2025].

8. Rada.gov.ua, (2014). *Pro vyshchu osvitu* [On Higher Education]. [online]. Kyiv, Ukraine. Available at: <http://zakon5.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1556-18/> [Accessed 29 June 2018].

9. Koval, L. M. (2021). *Mashynnyi pereklad u profesiinii pidhotovtsi perekladachiv* [Machine Translation in the Professional Training of Translators]. *Visnyk Kyivskoho natsionalnoho linhvistychnoho universytetu*, 24 (2), pp. 112–118.

Чемоданова Марина Федорівна. Постредагування машинного перекладу як освітня тенденція: прогнози на основі фактичних даних щодо філологічної освіти в Україні.

У статті розглядається постредагування машинного перекладу (Post-Editing Machine Translation, PEMT) як сучасний освітній тренд та перспективний напрям підготовки філологів і перекладачів в Україні. В умовах стрімкого розвитку цифрових технологій і штучного інтелекту машинний переклад дедалі активніше використовується в академічному й професійному середовищі, що зумовлює необхідність переосмислення традиційних підходів до перекладацької освіти. Наголошується, що некритичне або невідповідне використання МТ може негативно впливати на формування мовних, аналітичних і перекладацьких компетентностей студентів, що виявляє потребу в збалансованих педагогічних моделях.

PEMT визначається як затребувана професійна компетентність і важливий компонент сучасної перекладацької підготовки. Узагальнення результатів емпіричних досліджень свідчить, що системне навчання постредагуванню сприяє підвищенню якості перекладу, розвитку метамовної свідомості, критичного мислення та навичок аналізу помилок. Окрему увагу приділено інтеграції PEMT у навчальні плани закладів вищої освіти в Україні в контексті компетентнісного підходу та зростання ролі цифрової грамотності.

На основі міжнародного й національного досвіду обґрунтовуються доказові прогнози щодо подальшого впровадження постредагування машинного перекладу у філологічну освіту України як ефективного інструменту підготовки фахівців до вимог сучасного та майбутнього ринку перекладацьких послуг.

Ключові слова: переклад, редагування, методика викладання, мовна освіта, цифрова педагогіка, інновації в освіті, наукові конкурси, академічне письмо, перекладознавство, лінгвістика

Chemodanova Maryna. Post-Editing Machine Translation as an Educational Trend: Evidence-Based Predictions for Philological Education in Ukraine/

The article discusses post-editing machine translation (PEMT) as a modern educational trend and a promising direction for training philologists and translators in Ukraine. With the rapid development of digital technologies and artificial intelligence, machine translation is increasingly used in academic and professional environments, which necessitates a rethinking of traditional approaches to translation education. It is emphasized that uncritical or unprepared use of MT can negatively affect the formation of students' linguistic, analytical, and translation competencies, which reveals the need for balanced pedagogical models.

PEMT is defined as a sought-after professional competence and an important component of modern translation training. A summary of the results of empirical studies shows that systematic training in post-editing contributes to improving the quality of translation, developing metalinguistic awareness, critical thinking, and error analysis skills. Particular attention is paid to the integration of PEMT into the curricula of higher education institutions in Ukraine in the context of the competence-based approach and the growing role of digital literacy.

Based on international and national experience, evidence-based forecasts are made regarding the further implementation of post-editing of machine translation in philological education in Ukraine as an effective tool for training specialists to meet the requirements of the current and future translation services market.

Key words: PEMT, machine translation, post-editing, translator training, AI in education, translation pedagogy, digital linguistics, philology education.